

Heat Capacity and Thermodynamic Properties of Sr_2CoWO_6 and Sr_2NiWO_6

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The heat capacity (C_p) of the system Sr_2MWO_6 ($\text{M}=\text{Co}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}$) has been studied in the temperature range of 290-580 K. Anomalies in heat capacity were observed with a slight hump around 487 K and 526 K for Sr_2CoWO_6 and Sr_2NiWO_6 , respectively. These transitions appear to be associated with slight changes in band structure resulting from a structural (tetragonal \rightarrow cubic) transition.

PEROVSKITES and compounds crystallising in this modification have been studied extensively in view of their dielectric, magnetic and thermal properties. Perovskites offer a wide variation in composition by substitutions of A and B sites with cations of different valence states. Perovskites with hexavalent Mo or W were studied by Brixner¹. If hexavalent Mo or W ions are to be incorporated in perovskite with bivalent A ion, 50 mole percent of another bivalent ion of proper size must be introduced to preserve electrical neutrality. X-ray, dielectric and magnetic studies^{2,3} were done on compounds of the type $\text{Sr}_2\text{MMeWO}_6$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}^{2+}$ or Ni^{2+} ; $\text{M}=\text{W}^{6+}$ or Mo^{6+}). However, little information is available on the thermal properties of the above system. Hence, heat capacity measurements of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MMeWO}_6$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}^{2+}$ or Ni^{2+}) were undertaken to examine the type/temperature of transition and the results are discussed in this communication.

Experimental

The requisite amounts of AnalaR grade constituent oxides (except SrO which was weighed in the form of SrCO_3) were mixed by milling under acetone in an agate mortar and air dried. The dried mixtures were pre-fired below 1273 K in a platinum dish, ball milled and again fired for 4-6 hr between 1473 and 1573 K in air.

The final products were analysed by X-ray diffraction using CuK_α radiation ($\lambda=1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) and were characterised as single phase with tetragonal symmetry at room temperature; Sr_2CoWO_6 : $a=7.90 \text{ \AA}$, $c=7.94 \text{ \AA}$ and Sr_2NiWO_6 : $a=7.86 \text{ \AA}$, $c=7.90 \text{ \AA}$. (It may be mentioned here that since the cations at the B sites are ordered the unit cell edge must be doubled. Here $c=2c_0$ and $a=2a_0$ where c_0 and a_0 are the lattice constants of simple

perovskite unit cell). No extra lines due to any of the constituent oxides were detected within the sensitivity of the method.

The heat capacity, C_p , of the samples was measured in an adiabatic calorimeter which was calibrated using $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and ThO_2 as standards. Comparison of the observed data with NBS values indicated⁴ the accuracy to be about $\pm 2\%$, while the average scatter of experimental values from their own mean was 1.5%. The measurements were done in the temperature range of 290-580 K. In the neighbourhood of transition, shorter intervals of temperature (about 2°) were taken to study the detailed shape of the curve (Fig. 1).

Results and Discussion

The experimental molar heat capacities were determined in the same chronological order as measured to facilitate estimation of temperature increments in the measurement. Appropriate corrections were made for curvature to yield true differential heat capacities. Anomalies were observed with a slight hump around 487 K for Sr_2CoWO_6 and 526 K for Sr_2NiWO_6 , respectively. The molar heat capacity, entropy and enthalpy of these compounds are given in Table 1.

In compounds crystallising with perovskite like structure, the co-existence of magnetic and dielectric dipole ordering has been reported and the transition might arise out of magnetic (antiferro-para), ferroelectric (ferro-para) or structural (tetragonal-cubic) transitions.

The magnetic ordering in these compounds can be accounted for on the basis of indirect exchange interaction of the type $\text{Me}-\text{O}-\text{M}-\text{O}-\text{Me}$ as interpreted by Blasse⁵, whose magnetic susceptibility studies showed only one anomaly for each of the

Fig. 1

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF STRONTIUM TUNGSTEN COBALTATE AND NICKELATE

Temp. K	Sr_2CoWO_6			Sr_2NiWO_6		
	C_p J/mole. deg K	$H_T - H_{298}$ J/mole	$S_T - S_{298}$ J/mole. deg K	C_p J/mole. deg K	$H_T - H_{298}$ J/mole	$S_T - S_{298}$ J/mole. deg K
300	113.3	226.5	0.75	107.8	215.7	0.71
350	116.2	5969.0	18.47	112.9	5747.0	17.76
400	119.1	11867.0	34.19	117.0	11503.0	33.10
450	122.9	17915.0	48.45	120.0	17489.0	46.82
500	125.0	24365.0	62.03	122.9	23512.0	59.77
550	125.0	30560.0	73.82	124.1	29857.0	71.90

compounds of cobalt and nickel tungstate at 22 K and 54 K, respectively. The transition temperatures of 487 K and 526 K for Sr_2CoWO_6 and Sr_2NiWO_6 in our studies do not correspond to the reported values for magnetic transition. It appears, therefore, that the anomalies in the heat capacities are not due to the magnetic transition.

Dielectric studies⁶ of these compounds indicated the absence of sharp anomalies arising from any ferro- or anti-ferro-electric origin in the relevant temperature ranges.

From high temperature X-ray studies, the structural phase transition for Sr_2NiWO_6 was variously reported to be 533 K⁵, 573 K⁷ and 673 K⁸, respectively. As far as the authors are aware, no corresponding data for Sr_2CoWO_6 has been reported in the literature. The value of 533 K seems to be in good agreement with our heat capacity measurements. Further, electrical conductivity studies⁶ showed a break in the activation energy around

489 K for Sr_2CoWO_6 and around 533 K for Sr_2NiWO_6 . This observation is also in close agreement with our values of 487 K (Sr_2CoWO_6) and 526 K (Sr_2NiWO_6), respectively. Similar observations were made by us¹⁰ in the heat capacity studies on $\text{Sr}_2\text{CoMoO}_6$ and $\text{Sr}_2\text{NiMoO}_6$. It may, therefore, be concluded that the heat capacity anomalies observed in Sr_2CoWO_6 and Sr_2NiWO_6 are associated with slight changes in the band structure resulting from a structural (tetragonal \rightarrow cubic) transition.

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